

UNIVERSITY TRANSPORTATION CENTER
FOR UNDERGROUND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER (T2) PLAN

Submitted to

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Marte Gutierrez, Ph.D.
J. R. Paden Distinguished Professor and Director of UTC-UTI
Colorado School of Mines
Coolbaugh 308, 1012 14th St., Golden, CO 80401
Tel: (303) 273-3507, E-mail: mgutierr@mines.edu

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Signature:

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1. BACKGROUND

This Technology Transfer (referred hereinafter as “T2”) Plan is submitted by the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (hereinafter referred to as “UTC-UTI” or “Center”) to meet the latest “*Grant Deliverables and Reporting Requirements for 2016 University Transportation Centers*” (version 1.3, September 2017) set by the U.S. DOT for University Transportation Centers (UTCs) funded under the FAST Act.

This T2 plan is also in line with the U.S. DOT’s Strategic Plan for FY2018-2022 to “increase (in) production of DOT-funded tangible research outputs” as a performance measure. The strategic plan calls for the requirement of providing performance measures in terms of the number of tangible research outputs, outcomes and impacts for each UTC’s technology transfer plan. In this T2 plan, definitions for research outputs, outcomes, impacts and other research lifecycle terminologies use Table 1 which has been adapted from the U.S. DOT Research, Development and Technology Strategic Plan, FY2017-2021:

Table 1. Research Lifecycle Terminologies Used in the T2 Plan (adapted from the Strategic Plan established by the US DOT Office of the Assistant Secretary for Research and Technology).

Terminology	Definition
Agenda Setting	The act of evaluating the current and future state of the transportation system, identifying issues and problems that need to be addressed and developing a research agenda based on clearly defined research needs.
Research Need	A detailed account of a problem or issue that requires R&D activities to be resolved.
Research and Development (R&D)	R&D activities comprise creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of man, culture and society, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications
R&D Output	Any new or improved process, practice, technology, software, training aid, or other tangible product resulting from R&D activities.
Technology Transfer	Activities conducted to facilitate the adoption of R&D outputs. The Technology Transfer (T2) process runs in parallel with Agenda Setting and R&D activities.
Technology Deployment	Activities that demonstrate, pilot, or evaluate an R&D output, and/or facilitate the transfer of an R&D output to an adoption-ready state. Technology deployment is the final phase of the T2 process.
Adoption-Ready R&D Outputs	R&D outputs that are ready for full-scale operational use in the transportation system.
Adoption	The act of putting an adoption-ready R&D output into operational use in the transportation system.
R&D Outcome	Any changes made to the transportation system, or its regulatory, legislative, or policy framework, resulting from R&D outputs. Examples include the full-scale adoption of a new technology technique, or practice, or the passing of a new policy, regulation, rulemaking, or legislation.
R&D Impact	The impact of an R&D outcome on the transportation system, or society in general, such as reduced fatalities, decreased capital or operating costs, community impacts, or environmental benefits.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE T2 PLAN

The objectives of UTC-UTI T2 Plan are identical to those specified in the April 16, 2018 Memorandum by the US DOT Director of the Office of Research, Development and Technology:

- 1) Outline the people and organizations involved in the T2 Process, their roles, their assigned activities, and desired outcomes; and
- 2) Guide the development and potential adoption of UTC-UTI's outputs, outcomes and impacts.

UTC-UTI T2 ORGANIZATION

UTC-UTI T2 activities are planned according to the personnel and organizations listed in Table 2 together with their roles, mandates, functions and responsibilities.

Table 2. Personnel and Organizations Involved in UTC-UTI T2 Activities and Their Roles and Responsibilities.

Personnel and Organization	Roles and Responsibilities
Colorado School of Mines (CSM) Vice President of Research & Technology Transfer (VPRTT)	CSM's Chief research officer, responsible for: (1) oversight of Institutional Review Board (IRB), (2) research initiatives, and (3) technology transfer activities.
UTC-UTI Director	Responsible for: (1) overall performance of Center T2 activities, (2) identifying and prioritizing R&D agenda and projects, and (3) providing financial support to carry out research and T2 activities.
UTC-UTI Deputy Director and Associate Director for Industrial Collaboration and Technology Transfer	Responsible for: 1) collaborating with Center stakeholders, 2) developing strategies and activities for T2, and 3) setting and monitoring T2 metrics and targets.
Center Coordinators at Affiliate Universities	Responsible at their respective universities for: 1) implementation and conduct of Center T2 activities, 2) meeting and achieving assigned metrics and targets, and 3) ensuring compliance with their institutional rules and regulations.
Center PIs and Researchers	Duties include: 1) conduct the R&D, 2) manage research personnel, and 3) participate and provide support for Center T2 activities.
Advisory Board	Provide oversight and advice related to Center research and T2 activities.

Technology transfer activities for UTC-UTI will be established and conducted under the auspices of Colorado School of Mines (CSM) Office of Technology Transfer (OTT), which operates under the direction of CSM's Vice President of Research and Technology Transfer (VPRTT). The VPRTT is CSM's Chief Research Officer, and responsible for oversight of Institutional Review Board (IRB), research initiatives and technology transfer activities. CSM's OTT has established rules and regulations pertinent to T2 activities to ensure consistency and compliance with Federal and State laws and regulations. As a university center under the jurisdiction of CSM, UTC-UTI must comply with rules and regulations established by the VPRTT and OTT.

Within UTC-UTI, overall performance of T2 activities is managed by the Center Director, who is responsible for identifying and prioritizing R&D agenda, objectives and projects. The Director provides financial support to carry out research according to importance and relevance of projects, performance and track record of PIs, and availability of funds. In this T2 plan, the Director is mandated to ensure that Center activities and projects achieve maximum benefits to Center stakeholders (defined below).

Specific and operational T2 activities of UTC-UTI are carried out and managed by the Center Deputy Director and Associate Director for Industrial Collaboration and Technology Transfer. The Center Deputy/Associate Director shall: 1) liaise, communicate and collaborate with Center stakeholders to establish research needs and how these needs can be met by the Center, 2) develop strategies and activities for seamless technology transfer to Center stakeholders, and 3) set and regularly monitor specific metrics and targets to ensure success of T2 activities.

Center Coordinators at Affiliate Universities (California State University Los Angeles and Lehigh Universities) are responsible in their respective institutions for: 1) implementation and conduct of Center T2 activities, 2) meeting and achieving assigned metrics and targets, and 3) ensuring compliance with rules and regulations specific to their institutions. The last responsibility is important as University and State legal requirements may differ among the three intuitions.

PIs and Researchers funded by the Center are expected to: 1) conduct the R&D to develop desired technology, 2) manage research personnel (specifically post-doctoral research associates, graduate research assistants and laboratory/field personnel) in the conduct of R&D, and 3) participate in and provide support for Center T2 activities. Project PIs and researchers will work towards R&D activities that yield maximum benefit for Center stakeholders.

UTC-UTI's Advisory Board (AB) currently consists of members from the industry, state DOTs, Federal agencies and the academe. The AB meets annually to review Center progress and budgets, and helps provide direction on education, workforce development, diversity, industry collaboration, technology transfer and other Center activities.

3. UTC-UTI STAKEHOLDERS

UTC-UTI stakeholders are organizations that can directly or indirectly benefit and gain from the results of Center research activities. These organizations may be supporters who provide direct funds or cost match to specific research projects conducted by the Center, collaborators who jointly work on common research projects, and adopters and users of Center results and outcomes. Adopters are the first to be able to put the technology into operational use even if there is only limited acceptance of the product. They influence the wider use of the product by users. Users (e.g., the general public) are those able to use

the technology after the T2 process is complete and the technology is fully adopted and implemented. The different stakeholders will be the direct targets of UTC-UTI T2 efforts.

Table 3 lists the groups of expected UTC-UTI stakeholders and classifies them according to their potential roles. In Section 4.1, specific members of these groups will be identified and detailed steps to secure their involvement in Center research and T2 activities will be discussed.

Table 3. UTC-UTI Groups of Stakeholders and Their Potential Roles.

Groups of Stakeholders	Source of fund	Source of cost match	Collaborator	Adopter	User
Federal and State Agencies	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Construction Companies	?	Y	Y	Y	Y
Service Companies	?	Y	Y	Y	Y
Equipment & Materials Manufacturers	?	?	Y	Y	Y
Academic and Research Institutions	N	N	Y	Y	Y
Professional Associations	N	N	?	?	Y
Public	N	N	?	N	Y

Note: Y=Yes, N=No, and ?=Maybe

4. ELEMENTS OF THE UTC-UTI T2

This section discusses the different elements of the organization, implementation and performance monitoring of UTC-UTI's T2 plan.

4.1 Identifying and describing the involvement of stakeholders (including funding partners) in Center research program

Having identified the main groups of UTC-UTI's stakeholders together with their potential roles in Section 3, the main challenge is to identify specific stakeholders in each group and how they can be engaged in Center research activities. In working with stakeholders, UTC-UTI will follow the following principles:

- 1) Stakeholder engagement will be a core component throughout the lifecycle of its R&D activities, and
- 2) Transparency of its R&D efforts will be increased to build stakeholder confidence and improve research product transfer and adoption.

Table 4 identifies specific stakeholders and steps that will be done to reach out to each of the specific stakeholder to secure their engagement in Center R&D and eventually make them targets for adoption of technologies from UTC-UTI. It is important to note that many of the activities can be carried out in reciprocal and collaborative ways. For example, a software company can provide free license and access to their software. In turn, the Center can add new capabilities to the software that can be marketed by the software company. Another example is where UTC-UTI will work collaboratively with a stakeholder on a specific research project that will result in development of a joint intellectual property that can be declared through co-authorships in publications.

Table 4. UTC-UTI Specific Stakeholders and Steps to Secure their Engagement.

Specific stakeholder	Engagement in UTC-UTI research and T2
Federal and State Agencies	
FHWA	Funding for UTC-UTI projects.
State DOTs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Co-funding of UTC projects, 2) Providing data for use in research, 3) Access to State DOT facilities and tunnels for UTC-UTI personnel, 4) Internship for UTC-UTI students, and 5) Participation in UTC-UTI seminars, workshops and meetings.
Construction Companies	
Different construction and tunneling companies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Use of construction sites as test beds for research, 2) Providing data for use in research, 3) Internship for UTC-UTI students, 4) Co-authorship of joint reports and publications, and 5) Participation in UTC-UTI seminars, workshops and meetings.
Service Companies	
Consulting, design and management companies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Co-development of consulting, design and management tools, 2) Exchange of personnel, 3) Co-authorship of joint reports and publications, and 4) Participation in UTC-UTI seminars, workshops and meetings.
Software developers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Co-development and commercialization of software, 2) Access to and use of software, and 3) Use UTC-UTI projects as test beds for software.
Monitoring, inspection and repair/maintenance companies	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Co-development and commercialization of monitoring protocols and software, and sensor technologies, 2) Access to and free use of monitoring software and sensor technologies, and 3) Use of construction sites, and monitoring, inspection repair technologies as test beds for research.
Equipment & Materials Manufacturers	
Different construction and tunneling equipment and materials manufacturers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Co-development of new equipment and materials, 2) Testing and adoption of equipment and materials, and 3) Patenting and marketing of equipment and materials technologies.
Academic and Research Institutions	
Other UTCs, Universities and National Labs	Collaboration on research projects and dissemination efforts.
K-12 and college level educational institutions	Recruiting and training of students who will later work in the industry and help promote technologies developed by the Center.
Professional Associations	
TRB, ASCE, ASTM, ASEE and others	Sponsorship of forum for exchange of ideas and dissemination of research outcomes.
Public	
General public	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Popular dissemination of research results, and 2) Enhancing perception and acceptance of technology.

4.2 Assisting stakeholders in implementing and deploying research outputs

Assisting stakeholders in implementing and deploying research outputs is a crucial component of the UTC-UTI T2. The Center will interact with partners and stakeholders to provide mechanisms for stimulating technology transfer and turning research results directly into technological innovation. Technology transfer will be done in three ways:

- 1) Working closely and directly with stakeholders particularly various components of the underground transportation industry for direct technology transfer;
- 2) Sharing of innovations via continuing education, short courses, seminars and workshops; and
- 3) Dissemination through publications of research in journals and conference proceedings, reports, design manuals, and social media.

Industrial/Practitioner Partnership - This will be done through: a) Industry co-funded and focused research, and consulting projects; b) Collaboration on R&D projects, c) Testing, validation and deployment of technologies in stakeholder site or facilities; d) Exchange of personnel; and e) Training of students who will later work in the industry and help promote technologies developed by the Center. The Center will actively interact with project owners, designers and contractors in its R&D activities. One focus of the collaboration will be the implementation of research to existing and new underground infrastructures. The project team has extensive experience in working with industry. PIs who are part of the Center have collaborations with construction companies with funded projects from Kiewit, Jay Dee Contractors, The Robbins Company, BASF, Hayward Baker, and others forms of support from MAPTEK, Arup, Parsons Brinckerhoff, Geocomp, NYC MTA, LA Metro, Southern California Metropolitan Water District, CH2M Hill, AECOM, Brierley, CDM Smith, HNTB, Jacobs Associates, Mott MacDonald, MWH, Parsons, Shannon & Wilson. The Center will provide the foundation to further grow these industrial collaborations. In addition, Center researchers have been actively involved with Colorado Department of Transportation, the Federal Highway Administration, Transportation Research Board, and the US DOT through research projects.

Continuing Education and Technology Transfer Meetings- The Center will develop and hold short courses, workshops and webinars to accelerate technology transfer and assist stakeholders in implementing and deploying research outputs. The main goals of these meetings will be to introduce stakeholders on technological developments from the Center and their potential uses for their own benefits. Two continuing education short courses that will be co-organized/co-sponsored annually by UTC-UTI are on: a) Underground Grouting and Ground Improvement, and b) Tunneling Fundamentals. Free webinars of interest to industry will be organized regularly. UTC-UTI currently works with Trans-SET Center on twinning of webinars on topics of mutual interest. Another venue will be industry-focused workshops most of which will be held during the TRB Annual Meetings. There is a large constituent group with a clear need to have quality educational experiences that focus on state-of-the-art technologies and new approaches in the field of underground construction. Courses will be structured so they can be counted towards professional development hours needed for the PE license.

Dissemination of Research Results – Research dissemination through a wide range of media and outlets is discussed in detail in Section 4.5.

4.3 The commercialization process of research outputs

Commercialization of UTC-UTI outputs from CSM research will be carried out through CSM's Office of Technology Transfer (OTT). OTT has the expertise and track record in protection of intellectual property

and commercialization of research outcome of CSM faculty, researchers and staff. Commercialization of research products at California State University Los Angeles and Lehigh University will be made through their respective technology transfer organizations. Agreements will be made for research that will be carried out collaboratively among two or more universities that are part of UTC-UTI.

Commercialization of research outcomes at CSM is founded on the Bayh-Dole Act which gives U.S. universities the right to own rights to intellectual properties developed with U.S. government funds. Under this act, the university must: 1) report inventions arising from federally funded projects, 2) share revenues with inventors, and 3) have constraints on how technology is commercialized. The intellectual property must be licensed to a company that will exploit it to the advantage of the public. Preferences for licensing will be given to U.S. companies and small companies.

There are four avenues for potential commercialization of a research product: 1) patenting and licensing to enable research products to generate revenue; 2) partnership with an existing company who will market the product, 3) direct sale or licensing a product to an existing company; or 4) creation of a startup company that will further develop the research product for market release.

Intellectual property declaration and protection - Once it has been deemed to have market value and potential, the first step is to make an intellectual property declaration or public disclosure to protect it from potential infringement and secure its ownership. In many instances, publication in peer-reviewed journals can be a sufficient means to secure public disclosure and protect the intellectual property embodied in the publication. In turn, any commercialization agreement with organizations outside of the university will include provisions that will secure the right of researchers to disseminate and publish research results. Since the length to fully commercial research outcomes may exceed the duration of funding of the Center, the priority will be to secure intellectual property ownership then pave the way to eventual full commercialization.

In bringing research outcomes to the market, two types of plans will be developed:

- 1) *Development plan* - Technologies developed at universities typically require development to be ready for market. The effort and resources involved in this endeavor make it critically important that the adopters and users be focused and coordinated around a strategy for moving the technology to the market. A preliminary roadmap to how to bring the technology to the market is required.
- 2) *Business plan* – A business plan is a requirement before licensing research products. The business plan will outline the approach that will be used to bring the product to the market. The business plan will include: 1) The nature of the technology and what innovations/solutions it brings; 2) Competitive advantage of the technology; 3) Management team; 4) Production/Manufacturing plan; 5) Marketing plan; 6) Market/Opportunity size; 7) Intellectual Property plan; 8) Competition, and 9) Fiscal projections.

4.4 The collection and use of licensing revenues to provide further support for research and technology transfer

Revenue generation is a goal of UTC-UTI that is in line with CSM's institutional objectives for commercialization of research outcomes. At CSM, licensing and revenue generation from research outcomes are aimed to: 1) increase institutional revenues (shared with inventors); 2) promote economic

development for the state; 3) generate income to promote and support teaching and research; and 4) provide opportunities for more sponsored research.

The following principles established at CSM will be followed by UTC-UTI in planning for collecting and using licensing revenues from research outcomes:

- 1) *Pre-valuing intellectual property* – it is the nature of intellectual property that makes it difficult to assign them initial monetary value. As such, it will be necessary to negotiate in good faith the value of the intellectual property, once its created, and the adopters and users have determined they wish to pursue a license agreement.
- 2) *Licensing cost* - Licensing a technology yields the right to make, have made, use, lease, sell, and import products using the technology and to practice processes involving the technology. Usually entered into the costs of a license are: 1) the costs of filing and maintaining the patent; 2) a licensing fee; 3) royalties or yearly minimum payments from sales or sublicenses; and 4) milestone payments. The licensing cost must be included in estimating required revenue income from the commercialized research outcome.
- 3) *Start-up* – The potential to establish start-up companies will be studied as a good way to accelerate technology transfer and bringing technology to the market. Technologies based from research are, in general, in very early stages of development. They will need to solve not only a scientific problem, but a business or commercial problem. Ideally, the start-up must have intellectual property that is protected by a portfolio of patents. The university's policy also states that the researcher should have a plan which will bring in professional business management and the researchers' equity interest be diluted as more investment is attained.
- 4) *Revenue sharing* – Sharing of revenue from commercialization of research outcome will be in agreement with state law and university policy which allows the start-ups. Regulations allow for a share of the revenue to return (e.g., through indirect cost or IDC recovery) to the Center for further use in research and related activities.

4.5 The dissemination of research results

Wide dissemination of research results is an important component of technology transfer for two reasons: 1) it provides the first step in protecting the intellectual property of research outcomes, and 2) it enables peer-review to establish legitimacy and acceptance of the results among potential adopters and users. The following materials with focus on underground transportation infrastructure will be used for dissemination of research results:

- 1) Peer-reviewed journals (e.g., TRB, ASCE Journals, Tunneling and Underground Space Technology, Underground Space, etc.) provide the most rigorous validation of research work and the most reliable sharing of intellectual developments. Publications in peer-reviewed journals will be enhanced by participation of UTC-UTI researchers in the Editorial Boards of leading journals in the field.
- 2) Conferences, meetings, symposia and workshops (e.g., TRB Annual Meeting, ASCE, NAT, WTC, etc.) provide a rapid form of technology transfer. UTC-UTI participation in the leadership of the organization of meetings (e.g., through membership in organizing and scientific committees) will further enhance visibility of the Center and the work it carries out.
- 3) Technical reports, manuals, training materials, presentations from workshops and webinars, and popular articles will provide direct documentation of Center results and activities.

In addition to the above outlets, all materials produced by UTC-UTI (journal publication, and conference papers and presentations, reports, etc.) will be archived for wider public access in the website www.zonodo.org/utc_uti.

4.6 How corporate research support will be increased

UTC-UTI continues to engage the industry in its R&D efforts. Corporate participation and support of UTC-UTI research will be enhanced by co-funding of research projects either through cash or in-kind support. Research collaboration with industry will occur through access and use of construction sites and data in the testing and validation of analysis, modeling, design, construction, monitoring and retrofitting methodologies that are being developed in the Center, and through exchange of personnel.

4.7 How research outputs, outcomes and impacts will be tracked and reported.

Tracking and reporting of UTC-UTI research outputs, outcomes and impacts (defined in Table 1) are outlined below.

Research output will be tracked and reported in terms of the numbers of:

- 1) New or improved analysis, design and construction procedures;
- 2) Construction equipment and materials;
- 3) Sensors and sensing technologies;
- 4) Software;
- 5) Publications (papers, presentations, design manuals and training materials); and
- 6) Students and personnel trained

Research outcome will be tracked and reported in terms of the quantity of:

- 1) Analysis, design and construction procedures adopted by the industry;
- 2) Construction equipment and volume of construction materials used in actual projects;
- 3) Sensors and instances of use of sensing technology;
- 4) Software licenses used or sold;
- 5) Downloads and citations of publications, and
- 6) Trained students and personnel hired by industry.

Research impact will be tracked and reported in terms of:

- 1) Improved public perception and acceptance of tunnel constructions;
- 2) Increased number of tunnel constructions for transportation;
- 3) Reduction in time and cost of tunnel construction projects;
- 4) Reduction of construction injury and casualties;
- 5) Reduction in damage and traffic delays in tunnels during operation; and
- 6) Reduction in inspection, maintenance, and repair/retrofit frequency, duration and cost.

4.8 Technology transfer goals and performance measures

Table 5 presents the UTC-UTI T2 short-term and long-term specific goals, performance metrics and targets. The targets may be adjusted/re-calibrated periodically depending on how realistically they can be met.

Table 5. UTC-UTI T2 Short-Term and Long-Term Goals, Metrics and Targets.

Short-Term Goals, Metrics and Targets		
Goal	Metrics	Target per year
Conduct projects fully funded by Federal or State Transportation Agencies	Number of projects fully funded by Federal or State Transportation Agencies	1
Conduct R&D projects co-funded by stakeholder	Number of projects co-funded by state DOT and industry	3
	Number of projects with in-kind cost match from state DOT and industry	6
Work with stakeholders on collaborative research projects	Number of collaborative projects	3
	Number of publications published with stakeholders	6
	Number of stakeholder-sponsored student internships	4
	Number of stakeholder personnel working on projects	6
	Number of construction sites used for research	4
Disseminate results through publications	Number of papers published in peer-reviewed journals	8
	Number of papers published in conferences, symposia, workshops and meeting	18
	Number of technical reports published	3
	Number of popular articles published	2
Organize continuing education meetings and short courses	Number of short courses	2
	Number of workshops	2
	Number of webinar presentations	4
Train students and personnel who will become agents of T2	Number of students and personnel trained	4
Long-Term Goals, Metrics and Targets		
Goals	Metrics	Target for 5-years
Develop technologies for safe, cost-effective and sustainable UTIs	Number of analysis, modeling and design procedures with manuals	4
	Number of patent declarations	4
	Number of software developed and marketed	2
	Number of startups	1

5. REFERENCES

Some materials from the following references were used in the development of this T2 plan.

- 1) U.S. DOT Strategic Plan, FY2018-2022 - <https://www.transportation.gov/dot-strategic-plan>

- 2) USDOT Research, Development and Technology Strategic Plan, FY2017-2021 - <https://ntlsearch.bts.gov/inc/images/kms/StrategicPlan.pdf>
- 3) Building a Foundation for Effective Technology Transfer through Integration with the Research Process: A Primer - <https://rosap.ntl.bts.gov/view/dot/12262>
- 4) Colorado School Mines Resources for Technology Transfer - <http://inside.mines.edu/RES-Resources-Technology-Transfer>